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Everything Is Connected, No One Can Be Saved Alone; Vulnerability in the Context of Human Rights Law

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ABSTRACT

The concept of vulnerability is increasingly significant in contemporary human rights law, emphasizing that every individual is susceptible to harm and that no one is saved alone. This perspective recognizes vulnerability as an inherent part of the human condition, rather than a characteristic exclusive to specific groups. This article builds on this theoretical foundation to explore the concept of vulnerability in human rights law. It examines the concept of vulnerability in contemporary human rights law, with a focus on its theoretical underpinnings, legal framework, and practical implications. Through a critical analysis of relevant case law and academic literature, this article argues that vulnerability is a fundamental aspect of human rights law, emphasizing the importance of recognizing and responding to the universal susceptibility to harm. By situating the discourse within the Nigerian legal context, this study critically evaluates the constitutional guarantees in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended), legislative enactments and specialized legislation designed to protect vulnerable populations, such as the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act, the Child Rights Act, and the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act 2018. This study delineates the legal contours of vulnerability and assesses the efficacy of these statutory instruments in safeguarding the rights and dignity of vulnerable populations. Through comparative analysis, the study analyses how this concept has been interpreted and operationalized within the legal systems of Nigeria, the United Kingdom, South Africa and globally, it highlights the varied approaches these jurisdictions adopt in protecting vulnerable groups, considering the influence of international human rights norms and judicial interpretations. Ultimately, this study seeks to inform and enrich the ongoing dialogue on interconnected vulnerabilities and the need for human rights protection for all in Nigeria, with a view to providing recommendations that is aimed at fostering a more inclusive and equitable society that will bring about a paradigm shift from an atomistic, individual-rights-centered model toward one that embraces relationality, solidarity, and collective responsibility to meet International best practices.

Keywords: Human Rights, Vulnerability, Vulnerability as a Universal Human Rights condition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, human rights frameworks were designed to protect individuals from State excesses, with little emphasis on the social and structural disadvantages faced by certain groups.² However, it is argued that vulnerability is an inherent part of the human condition, rather than a characteristic unique to specific

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² A. F. Vrdoljak *Human Rights and Genocide: The Work of Lauterpacht and Lemkin in Modern International Law*, the European Journal of International Law (2009) Vol. 20 No 4, 1163-1194

groups³. Vulnerability is universal and it is essential to acknowledge and respond to it in a way that promotes equality and justice⁴. This has made the concept of vulnerability to gain significant attention in human rights law, particularly in the context of marginalized and disadvantaged groups.

The phrase “everything is connected and no one is saved alone” captures a profound truth about the human condition: the interdependence of individuals, communities, and nations, it reflects a paradigm shift from an atomistic, individual-rights-centered model toward one that embraces relationality, solidarity, and collective responsibility. The modern landscape of international human rights law is shaped by the recognition that human beings are deeply interconnected in existence. This interconnectedness becomes especially visible in moments of crisis—whether pandemics, economic inequality, armed conflict, climate change, or mass displacement—where the vulnerability of one group has repercussions for the whole, illustrating that the protection of rights cannot be pursued in isolation. Within the framework of contemporary international human rights law, vulnerability has emerged as a key lens through which the dignity and rights of individuals and groups are understood and protected. The concept of vulnerability emerges as both a descriptive and normative tool, emphasizing the universal yet differentiated susceptibility of human beings to harm, and the corresponding duties of States and international institutions to ensure protection. The recognition of vulnerability challenges purely individualistic conceptions of rights, emphasizing instead solidarity, mutual responsibility, and collective protection.

The maxim “everything is connected and no one is saved alone” underscores a central truth of human rights law: the dignity, security, and well-being of individuals are inextricably bound to collective structures of protection. At a time when climate change, pandemics, armed conflicts, forced migration, and technological disruptions transcend borders, human rights law must grapple with vulnerability as both a universal human condition and a structural reality. This article explores the role of vulnerability within the framework of contemporary international human rights law. It examines the philosophical and legal foundations of vulnerability, its recognition in treaties and jurisprudence, and its implications for States’ obligations in a globalized and interdependent order. This article builds on this theoretical foundation to explore the concept of vulnerability in human rights law.

2. CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS

2.1. HUMAN RIGHTS

Human Rights has been defined as rights that belongs to every person and do not depend on the specifics of the individual or the relationship between the right holder and the right guarantor. In the same vein these rights have been defined as those minimum rights which every individual must have against the State or other authority by virtue of being a member of the human family.⁵ They are those rights which are inherent in our state of nature and without which we cannot live as human beings.⁶ Human Rights are claims that ought to have legal and moral protection to ensure that basic needs are met.⁷ They are claims which are invariably supported by law, made on society, especially on its official managers by individuals or groups on the basis of their humanity.⁸

³ M. A. Fineman *The Vulnerable Subject : Anchoring Equality in the Human Condition*, *Havard Journal of Law & Gender*, (2008) 31, 367-399

⁴ J. Butler *Prekarious Life: Powers of Mourning and Violence*, London Verso Books (2004)

⁵ O. W. Igwe *The Human Right to be Different: Context, Vulnerability, Values, Realities and Consequences*, An Inaugural Lecture of the Rivers State University, Faculty of Law, delivered on Wednesday 25th September 2024.

⁶ O. Byerene, J. Darre (2005) *Human Rights: An Introduction* (Singapore: Pearson Education) 5 Mishra Pramod (2000) *Human Rights Global Issues*, (Delhi Kalpaz Publications), 4

⁷ R. T. Vincent, (1986) *Human Rights and International Relations* (Cambridge University Press), 12-14

⁸ U. O. Umozurike (1997) *The African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights* (Martinus Nijhoff Publishers) 4

2.2. VULNERABILITY CONCEPT

The concept of "universal vulnerability" suggests that vulnerability is inherent to the human condition, and institutions can either exacerbate or mitigate this vulnerability. This perspective emphasizes the need for supportive systems to protect human rights⁹. As the appraisal of vulnerability is undertaken, it is needful to commence on the note that violation of human rights endures at the fault lines where fault lines are taken to be the range of susceptibility the lowest ebb of weakness that attracts any seeming object or substance.¹⁰

In the context of human rights, vulnerability refers to the susceptibility of individuals or groups to harm, exploitation, abuse, or neglect due to various factors¹¹ such as personal, social, economic, political, or environmental factors. Vulnerable individuals or groups often lack the capacity to protect themselves or claim their rights without assistance or legal safeguards.

Vulnerability is not just a descriptive term but a normative concept, it implies State obligations to recognize and respond to the particular needs of these individuals or groups to ensure substantive equality and dignity. Individuals may experience multiple forms of discrimination or vulnerability due to intersecting factors such as gender, race, disability, age, socio-economic status and others.

2.3. VULNERABILITY AS A UNIVERSAL HUMAN CONDITION

Vulnerability is not just about being susceptible to harm, but also about the social, economic, and institutional structures that contribute to this susceptibility. Vulnerability is not merely a situational disadvantage; it is a universal human condition.

As legal theorist Martha Fineman argues, vulnerability arises from the embodied nature of human existence and the inevitable dependency that accompanies it. Fineman's vulnerability thesis posits that the State has an affirmative obligation to ensure that human rights apply meaningfully to all, particularly those who are disproportionately vulnerable.¹² Illness, disability, poverty, migration, and aging expose the fact that all human beings rely on structures of support, and that rights cannot be safeguarded in isolation. Contemporary human rights law, therefore, cannot be effective without addressing the relational and systemic dimensions of vulnerability.

2.4. INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS LAW

International Human Rights Law (IHRL) is a set of rules and principles that govern the protection and promotion of human rights globally. It is primarily concerned with the embedding of universally recognized human rights, most often contained within international treaties, within the realm of international law, enjoining States to protect people within their jurisdiction from abuses involving their inherent rights¹³.

A core focus of international human rights law is the protection of vulnerable and marginalized populations from abuse, exploitation and other widespread or systematic abuses. A concern for people living in conditions of vulnerability is a core tenet of International Human Rights Law and a primary area of concern for human rights non-governmental organization actors.¹⁴

3. KEY ASPECTS OF VULNERABILITY IN HUMAN RIGHTS LAW

3.1. Universal Vulnerability: Recognizing that every individual is susceptible to harm and that vulnerability is an inherent part of the human condition.

⁹ R. Croucher *Vulnerability and the Law* University of New South Wales Law Journal 2018 Vol. 41 (3) <http://humanrights.gov.au> accessed 17 June 2025

¹⁰ O. W. Igwe n(5)

¹¹ E. Gordon-Bouvier *The Vulnerable Subject: Anchoring Equality in the Human Condition (Martha Fineman)* <http://radar.brookes.ac.uk> accessed 17 June 2025

¹² M. A. Fineman n(3)

¹³ M. Brodowicz *the Effectiveness of International Human Rights Law in Protecting Vulnerable Populations* <https://aithor.com/essay-examples/the-effectiveness-of-international-human-rights-law-in-protecting-vulnerable-populations> accessed 2 October , 2025

¹⁴ *ibid*

3.2. Social and Institutional Structures: Understanding that vulnerability is shaped by social, economic, and institutional structures that contribute to susceptibility to harm.

3.3. State Responsibility: Acknowledging the state's affirmative obligation to protect individuals from harm and ensure that human rights apply meaningfully to all.

3.4. Intersectionality: Recognizing that vulnerability can be exacerbated by intersecting forms of discrimination, inequality, and structural and societal dynamics.¹⁵

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

4.1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human vulnerability has been increasingly theorized in recent decades. The concept of vulnerability is grounded in the recognition that every individual is susceptible to harm and that vulnerability is an inherent part of the human condition. This perspective emphasizes the importance of collective responsibility in ensuring the protection of human rights. The theoretical framework of vulnerability is informed by various disciplines, including sociology, philosophy, and law. In perusing the development of vulnerability in human rights law key institutions, international legal instruments and works of some scholars would be reviewed below in order to buttress the points of vulnerability and human rights.

A deep perception to the nature of human rights can be traced to the **Charter of the United Nations**¹⁶, it was committed to the purpose and principles, the realization of which in the light of the changing world conditions required substantial adaptation of institutional and procedural arrangements. The strong persuasion in the clauses concerning human rights in the Charter provide the foundation for an impetus to further implement the protection and promotion of human rights.¹⁷

The Charter embodied limitations on the State's freedom of action and also made provisions for the development of human rights through each Nation's constitution, thus, providing a constitutional basis for achieving international peace, security and wellbeing.¹⁸ United Nations treaty and Human Rights bodies and special rapporteurs have integrated vulnerability assessments into their interpretations of international human rights treaties, highlighting intersectional and compounded vulnerabilities, particularly in contexts of poverty, conflict, and discrimination.

O. W. Igwe sees human rights as cherished entitlements endowed upon every person in virtue only of being a human and which are not extinguishable (even when they are massive, consistent and systematic) as they carry the status of innateness, being inherent, inalienable and therefore immutable.¹⁹ He further stated that in looking at human rights from a vulnerability approach, the State must be responsive to the realities of human vulnerability and its corollary, social dependency, including situations reflecting inherent or necessary inequality when it initially establishes or sets up mechanisms to monitor these relationships and institutions.²⁰

Martha Albertson Fineman, a pioneer in vulnerability studies, argues that vulnerability is "the universal, inevitable, enduring aspect of the human condition". It shifts attention away from group-based claims of disadvantage to the structural and institutional responsibilities of the state in creating conditions for resilience.²¹ She argued for the recognition of universal vulnerability as an inherent aspect of the human condition. She contends that the State must adopt a responsive and responsible approach to

¹⁵ R. Cover, *Law Without Violence: Human Rights Adjudication as World Building* Harvard Law Review (2024) Vol. 137 No. 5, 1403-1424

¹⁶ Signed at San Francisco on June 26, 1945

¹⁷ O. W. Igwe n(5)

¹⁸ L. M. Goodrich et al (1969) *Charter of the United Nations, Commentary and Documents* (New York: Columbia University Press) 1

¹⁹ O. W. Igwe (2002) *Preliminary Studies in Human Rights law* (Lago; Rings and Favolit Ltd) 6

²⁰ O. W. Igwe n(5)

²¹ M. A. Fineman, 'The Vulnerable Subject: Anchoring Equality in the Human Condition', *Yale Journal of Law and Feminism* (2008) 20; *ibid* n (3)

address both individual and institutional sources of vulnerability through proactive legal and policy frameworks.²² In her view she states that while vulnerability theory begins with vulnerability it does not end there. In fact, it is the implication of human vulnerability that are the most significant part of the theory for legal and political thought because we are embodied creatures, we are also dependent on social institutions and relationship throughout life.²³

Sociologist Bryan Turner advanced the notion of embodied vulnerability, emphasizing the biological and social conditions that expose individuals to harm, thus reinforcing the need for human rights protections that address both physical and social disadvantages.²⁴

Sandra Fredman linked vulnerability to the concept of substantive equality, advocating for legal frameworks that address not only formal inequality but also the structural and social disadvantages that sustain vulnerability.²⁵

Judith Butler, in *Precarious Life*, highlights the relational aspect of vulnerability, noting that human life is always sustained through networks of social, political, and environmental interdependence²⁶. This resonates with the notion that “no one is saved alone,” as dignity and survival cannot be secured in isolation but require collective structures of care and protection.

The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR)²⁷ has significantly operationalized vulnerability by recognizing heightened obligations toward vulnerable groups, including asylum seekers, detainees, children, and persons with disabilities. Notable cases like *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece*²⁸ (2011) have expanded the scope of state responsibility under Article 3 of the ECHR.

From the views of these scholars, international institutions and legal instruments as well as from a legal-ethical standpoint, vulnerability thus challenges the classical liberal view of the rights-bearer as an autonomous, self-sufficient individual, instead, it situates human rights within a web of interconnections, solidarity, and mutual obligations. We see that vulnerability theory challenges inaccurate vision of legal subjectivity, it calls for a State that is responsive to human needs and for the reorganization of many existing structures which are currently based on a conception of legal order that unduly valorized individual liberty and choices and ignores the realities of human dependency and vulnerability.²⁹ Vulnerability suggest that a legal subject is defined by vulnerability and need, rather than exclusively by rationality and liberty, more fully reflects the human condition.³⁰

The need to understand that Vulnerability is not a deficit but a universal condition that requires responsive legal and institutional frameworks is therefore called and needs to be awakened or revived in actions of Sovereign States to bring about cooperation and a unified front.

4.2. VULNERABILITY AS A LENS IN CONTEMPORARY HUMAN RIGHTS LAW

Vulnerability theory has gained traction in international human rights discourse, especially through the works of Martha Fineman and later scholars who argue that vulnerability is not a condition confined to certain groups but a universal human characteristic. All human beings are susceptible to harm due to their embodied existence and dependence on social, economic, and political structures.

In contemporary human rights law, vulnerability plays two roles:

²² E. Gordon-Bouvier n (11)

²³ M. A. Fineman ‘Vulnerability and Social Justice’ *Valparaiso University Law review*, (2019) 53 (2) 341-370

²⁴ B. S. Turner *Vulnerability and Human Rights* (Penn State University Press 2006)

<http://doi.org/10.5323/j.ctt7v124>, <http://www.jstor.org> accessed 17 June 2025

²⁵ S. Fredman *Substantive Equality Revisited* *International Journal of Constitutional*, Volume 14, Issue 3 July 2016 712-738 <http://academic.oup.com>; S. Fredman *The Concept of Vulnerability and its relation to the Concepts of Inequality and Discrimination-A Review Article* <http://www.researchgate.net> accessed 17 June 2025

²⁶ J. Butler n (4)

²⁷ Founded on 21 January 1959 in Rome, Italy. It is based in Strasbourg and It is an International court of the Council of Europe which interprets the European Convention on Human Rights

²⁸ (2011) European Court of Human Rights, App. No 30696/09

²⁹ O. W. Igwe n(5)

³⁰ M. A. Fineman ‘*Vulnerability and Inevitable Inequality*’ (2017) 4 *Oslo L. Rev.* 133, 149

- a. **Universal Vulnerability** – Recognition that all human beings, by virtue of their humanity, are vulnerable. This challenges narratives that divide the world into “protected” and “unprotected,” emphasizing that international cooperation is essential in safeguarding dignity³¹. For instance, the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted that vulnerability to disease disregards borders and that vaccine inequity undermines collective global health. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights³² embodies the recognition of inherent human dignity and equal rights as safeguards against universal vulnerability to oppression and violence.
- The two Covenants on Universal Human Rights further institutionalize protections that address vulnerabilities to state power, poverty, and deprivation. For example, ICCPR guarantees the right to life³³, ICESCR protect the rights to an adequate standard of living and health³⁴. These provisions reflect the idea that all human beings, by virtue of their embodied existence, are vulnerable to deprivation and thus require rights guarantees.
- b. **Particular Vulnerability** – While vulnerability is universal, international law also acknowledges differentiated vulnerabilities; certain groups, such as refugees, women, children, persons with disabilities, and minorities, face heightened risks of harm due to structural inequalities, discrimination, or conflict. International human rights law, through instruments like the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)³⁵ or the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)³⁶, recognizes the need for tailored protections to address these differentiated vulnerabilities.

4.3. THE PHILOSOPHICAL AND LEGAL ROOTS OF INTERCONNECTEDNESS

The principle of interconnectedness is not new, philosophical traditions from Ubuntu in Africa to cosmopolitanism in European thought affirm that humanity is bound together in mutual dependence. In legal discourse, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)³⁷ declared that “all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights,”³⁸ anchoring the idea that rights transcend borders and that the protection of one cannot be divorced from the protection of all.

Subsequent human rights treaties including the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)³⁹ and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)⁴⁰ illustrate the indivisibility and interdependence of rights. The recognition that no right can be fully realized without others reflects the idea that everything is connected: political participation is meaningless without freedom of expression, while the right to health cannot be realized without adequate food, housing, and environmental protection.

4.4. HUMAN RIGHTS LAW AND INTERCONNECTED VULNERABILITIES

International human rights law, as articulated in instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁴¹ (1948), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights⁴², and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights⁴³, is founded on the idea of universal dignity. Yet, the application of these norms reveals that the realization of one person’s rights is often tied to the conditions of others.

³¹ M. A. Fineman, n (3)

³² Universal Declaration of Human Rights, UNGA Res 217 A (III), 10 December 1948

³³ Treaty Series Vol. 999 p.171 (1966), Article 6

³⁴ Treaty Series Vol. 993 p.3 (1966), Articles 11 and 12

³⁵ Treaty Series Vol. 1577 p.3 (1989)

³⁶ Un General Assembly Resolution A/RES/61/106 adopted in December 13, 2006

³⁷ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, UNGA Res 217 A (III), 10 December 1948

³⁸ *ibid*

³⁹ Treaty Series Vol. 999 p.171 (1966)

⁴⁰ Treaty Series Vol. 993 p.3 (1966)

⁴¹ United Nations General Assembly, Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948, UN Doc. A/RES/217/A (III)

⁴² Treaty Series Vol. 999 p.171 (1966)

⁴³ Treaty Series Vol. 993 p.3 (1966)

For instance:

The contemporary human rights regime increasingly grapples with problems that cannot be solved within State borders: for instance:

- a. **Climate Change:** Rising sea levels, desertification, and natural disasters affects entire population, making climate justice a collective human rights issue and threaten the right to life, housing, and self-determination of small island states. Climate-related migration underscores that “no one is saved alone,” as environmental harm in one region generates displacement and conflict elsewhere. Vulnerability to environmental harm transcends borders, reinforcing the need for cooperative frameworks. The 2021 UN Human Rights Council Resolution 48/13 recognized the right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment. UN Human Rights Committee, 2020, the Committee recognized that climate-induced displacement may trigger protection under the right to life⁴⁴.
- b. **Public Health and Pandemics:** The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted that the right to health cannot be secured individually. COVID-19 revealed systemic vulnerabilities in global health governance. States’ failure to cooperate in equitable vaccine distribution highlighted the moral and legal imperative for solidarity. The vulnerability of marginalized groups, lack of equitable vaccine distribution, and fragile health systems in certain regions created global risks, showing that no state or person could be “saved alone.”
- c. **Digital Technology:** Surveillance, misinformation, and algorithmic discrimination transcend national jurisdictions, raising questions about the universality of privacy, freedom of expression, and equality online. The UN Human Rights Council Resolution 68/167 (2013) on digital privacy shows that vulnerability in cyberspace transcends borders, raising extraterritorial obligations to protect privacy and data.
- d. **Armed Conflicts, Migration and Refugees:** Displacement due to war or economic hardship underscores the shared responsibility of the international community to protect asylum seekers and refugees, in line with instruments like the 1951 Refugee Convention. Wars in one region generate refugee flows, destabilizing neighboring states and requiring international burden-sharing under instruments such as the 1951 Refugee Convention⁴⁵.
- e. **Migration and Refugees:** Displacement due to war or economic hardship underscores the shared responsibility of the international community to protect asylum seekers and refugees, in line with instruments like the 1951 Refugee Convention.

5. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The Nigerian legal framework, comprising the 1999 Constitution, domestic statutes, and international treaties, implicitly addresses vulnerability, particularly through protections for children, women, and persons with disabilities from human rights violations. Laws such as the Child Rights Act and the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act reflect group-based vulnerability protections, these Nigerian Statutes Governing Vulnerability in Human Rights Law include:

5.1. CONSTITUTION OF THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA, 1999 (AS AMENDED)⁴⁶:

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) is the cornerstone of human rights protection. It provides fundamental rights and freedoms for all citizens, including protection from discrimination. Chapter IV guarantees fundamental rights such as Right to life,⁴⁷ Right to dignity,⁴⁸ Right to personal liberty,⁴⁹ Freedom of expression and association,⁵⁰ Right to freedom from discrimination.⁵¹

⁴⁴ ICCPR Article 6

⁴⁵ L. Peroni and A. Timmer *Vulnerable Groups: The Promise of an Emerging Concept in European Human Rights Convention Law* (2013) International Journal of Constitutional Law 11 (4)

⁴⁶ CFRN 1999 (as amended)

⁴⁷ Ibid Section 33

However, the Constitution does not explicitly define or protect vulnerable groups, which weakens the enforceability of targeted protection because vulnerability can lead to human rights violations like in;

- a. Right to life and security there can be increased risk of violence, abuse, and exploitation.
- b. Right to equality and non-discrimination there can be unequal access to education, employment, and healthcare.
- c. Right to dignity and autonomy there can be limited ability to make choices and decisions.

5.2. DISCRIMINATION AGAINST PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES (PROHIBITION) ACT⁵²:

This Act prohibits discrimination against persons with disabilities and promotes their integration into society.⁵³ It serves as a key legislation protecting disability rights as it seeks to protect the rights of persons with disabilities. The Act further provides for penalty for offenders⁵⁴ however in spite of these fixed penalties this law has continuously been abused and its application is still minimal.

5.3. CHILD RIGHTS ACT 2003⁵⁵:

This Act has been domesticated in only some States of the Federation; it provides broad protections for the rights and welfare of children in Nigeria. Due to lack of domestication in some States and blatant refusal to adhere to the said Act especially in the Northern parts of the Federation it faces the challenges of implementation and enforceability. This is seen in cases of Child marriages and restrictions in access to education by the girl child in some parts of Northern Nigeria.

5.4. VIOLENCE AGAINST PERSONS PROHIBITION (VAPP) ACT⁵⁶:

This Act addresses violence of all forms and discrimination, it aims to prevent and eliminate violence in public and private life of individuals, particularly women and girls. It provides protection for victims. The Act like its counterpart has similar challenge of implementation and enforcement.

5.5. NATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS COMMISSION ACT⁵⁷:

This Act has conferred on the Commission independence and strengthened its power with respect to promotion and protection of human rights, investigation of alleged violation of human rights and enforcement of decisions. The Act gives the Commission power to vet legislations at all levels to ensure their compliance with human rights norms. In spite of the additional powers conferred on the Commission it still lags behind in implementation and enforcement.

5.6. THE ROLE OF THE STATE IN ADDRESSING VULNERABILITY

International human rights law lays down obligations which States are bound to respect. States must refrain from interfering with or curtailing human rights, it must protect individuals and groups against human rights abuses and it must take positive actions to facilitate the enjoyment of basic human rights⁵⁸.

Under International law like International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights⁵⁹, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights⁶⁰, Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of

⁴⁸ Ibid Section 34

⁴⁹ Ibid Section 35

⁵⁰ Ibid Section 39-40

⁵¹ Ibid Section 42

⁵² Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018

⁵³ Ibid Section 1 (1)

⁵⁴ Ibid Section 1 (2)

⁵⁵ Child's Rights Act 2003, Act No.26 of 2003, Cap. C. 50, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria

⁵⁶ VAPP Act 2015, it was passed in May 2015

⁵⁷ Cap N46 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 amended in 2010 as National Human Rights Commission (Amendment) Act 2010

⁵⁸ International Human Rights Law, <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-and-mechanisms/international-human-rights-law> accessed 1 October 2025

⁵⁹ Treaty Series Vol. 999 p.171 (1966)

⁶⁰ Treaty Series Vol. 993 p.3 (1966)

Discrimination Against Women⁶¹, Convention on the Rights of the Child⁶², to which Nigeria is a party, States have a positive obligation to protect the vulnerable in areas of preventing violations, providing redress for abuse, ensuring access to healthcare, education, and social services however in practice, Nigeria often fails to meet these obligations due to weak institutions, corruption, and political interference.

While Nigeria has yet to adopt a universal vulnerability framework akin to Fineman's theory, the influence of UN treaty bodies and the African human rights system has encouraged recognition of vulnerabilities in areas such as gender-based violence and the plight of internally displaced persons, these statutes provide a framework for protecting vulnerable individuals and groups, enforcement remains a significant challenge. Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts from government agencies, civil society organizations, and other stakeholders.

Nigerian courts have often taken a formalistic approach to human rights, focusing on procedural issues rather than substantive protection of vulnerable persons. However, in some cases like **Uzoukwu v. Ezeonu II**⁶³, courts have interpreted constitutional rights broadly to advance justice. Yet, the lack of public interest, litigation culture, access to legal aid, and judicial delay limit the use of courts in protecting the vulnerable.

5.7. LEGAL IMPLICATIONS OF INTERCONNECTED VULNERABILITY

a. From Individual to Collective Rights

While civil and political rights emphasize individual freedoms, contemporary human rights law increasingly acknowledges collective or "solidarity rights." The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights⁶⁴ explicitly recognizes peoples' rights to development⁶⁵, peace⁶⁶, and a healthy environment⁶⁷. These provisions embody the principle that no one is saved alone.

b. Solidarity, Third-Generation Rights and Collective Responsibility

The notion that "no one is saved alone" demands a shift from a strictly individualistic framework to a solidarity-based understanding of human rights⁶⁸. Solidarity here is not charity but a legal and ethical imperative that acknowledges mutual dependence. Mechanisms such as international cooperation, humanitarian intervention, and sustainable development goals operationalize this principle, emphasizing that the protection of human rights is a shared duty. These interconnected vulnerabilities reaffirm that human rights protection must be both global and collaborative.

Solidarity rights or "third-generation rights" emerged in the 1970s, encompassing rights to development, peace, and environmental sustainability. The UN Declaration on the Right to Development⁶⁹ and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development⁷⁰ (2015) illustrate how interconnectedness requires cooperative efforts among states, international institutions, and civil society.

c. Extraterritorial Obligations (ETOs)

Given the globalized nature of vulnerability, States' duties cannot stop at their borders. The Maastricht Principles on Extraterritorial Obligations in the Area of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights⁷¹ 2011 articulate that States have duties to avoid causing or contributing to human rights violations abroad,

⁶¹ Treaty Series Vol. 1249 p.13 (1979)

⁶² Treaty Series Vol. 1577 p.3 (1989)

⁶³ (1991) 6 NWLR (Pt. 200) p. 708

⁶⁴ Adopted June 27, 1981, OAU Doc. CAB/LEG/67/3 rev.5

⁶⁵ Ibid, Article 22

⁶⁶ Ibid, Article 23

⁶⁷ Ibid, Article 24

⁶⁸ Pope Francis, *Fratelli Tutti: On Fraternity and Social Friendship* (2020) Vatican City

⁶⁹ UN General Assembly, Resolution 41/128, 4 December 1986

⁷⁰ Adopted on September 25, 2015

⁷¹ Published in Human Rights Quarterly in 2012, Volume 29 issue 4; <https://doi.org/10.1177/016934411102900411> accessed 1 October 2025

particularly in relation to environmental harm, corporate accountability, and international economic policies.

d. Institutional Responsiveness

Vulnerability theory emphasizes the need for resilient and responsive institutions. Courts such as the Inter-American Court of Human Rights and the European Court of Human Rights have adopted vulnerability reasoning. In González et al. (*"Cotton Field"*) v. Mexico⁷², the Inter-American Court recognized women as subjects of special protection due to structural gender-based vulnerabilities. The European Court has similarly invoked vulnerability in cases concerning asylum seekers *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece*⁷³.

5.8. THE IMPORTANCE OF ADDRESSING VULNERABILITY AND THE IMPLICATIONS FOR INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS LAW

Addressing vulnerability is crucial for promoting human rights and dignity. By recognizing the universal susceptibility to harm, we can work towards creating a more just and equitable society where everyone's human rights are respected and protected⁷⁴.

The principle that "everything is connected and no one is saved alone" reshapes how international human rights law is interpreted and applied:

- a. **From Sovereignty to Solidarity** – While State sovereignty remains central, it cannot justify isolationism in the face of transnational threats. Human rights obligations extend beyond borders, as reflected in evolving doctrines of extraterritorial application.
- b. **Collective Responsibility** – International cooperation, as mandated under the UN Charter and human rights treaties, is no longer optional but a necessity for survival in an interconnected world.
- c. **Transformative Justice** – Addressing vulnerability requires not only protection from immediate harm but also structural reforms to dismantle inequality, exclusion, and discrimination.
- d. **Human Rights as Relational** – Rights are not abstract entitlements possessed in isolation; they are sustained through interdependence, community, and global solidarity.

5.9. CHALLENGES AND CRITIQUES

While the concept of vulnerability has been instrumental in advancing human rights, the incorporation of vulnerability into international human rights law also faces obstacles, challenges and critiques. Some argue that the concept can be used to stigmatize and stereotype certain groups, undermining their agency and autonomy. Others contend that the focus on vulnerability might detract from addressing the root causes of human rights violations⁷⁵.

Compliance of human rights law is not just a question of whether or how a State has violated an International Human Rights Treaty but a question of whether victims who are not typically in the position to seek judicial redress are able to obtain reliefs as human rights law is the minimum floor that is what is to be expected and required for basic human dignity throughout the world⁷⁶. Therefore, despite its normative power, vulnerability as a legal principle faces challenges:

- a. **State Sovereignty vs. Collective Responsibility:** States often resist external scrutiny, invoking sovereignty to avoid obligations toward vulnerable populations within or beyond their borders.
- b. **Resource Inequalities:** The realization of rights for vulnerable groups requires redistribution of resources, which raises political and economic tensions.

⁷² Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACHR) Series, IHLR 4151 (IACHR 2009), 16 November 2009 (IACtHR)

⁷³ App. No. 30696/09 European Court of Human Rights 2011

⁷⁴ M. A. Fineman, *The Vulnerable Subject and the Responsive State* Emory Law Journal 2010

⁷⁵ M. A. Fineman n (74)

⁷⁶ M. Brodowicz *the Effectiveness of International Human Rights Law in Protecting Vulnerable Populations* <https://aithor.com/essay-examples/the-effectiveness-of-international-human-rights-law-in-protecting-vulnerable-populations> accessed 2 October , 2025

c. Risk of Paternalism: Overemphasis on vulnerability may unintentionally reinforce stereotypes of weakness or dependence, undermining the agency of individuals and groups.

d. Overgeneralization: The universality of vulnerability risks diluting its analytical utility unless combined with attention to structural inequalities.

e. State Capacity: Expansive obligations to address interconnected vulnerabilities may be impractical for states with limited resources.

f. Global Inequality: While vulnerability is shared, protective responses are uneven. Wealthier States often insulate themselves while neglecting solidarity with poorer States—evident in vaccine nationalism during COVID-19⁷⁷.

Nonetheless, vulnerability offers a vital corrective to overly individualistic and State-centric conceptions of rights.

6. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS WITH OTHER JURISDICTIONS:

This is carried out in order to explore how the concept of vulnerability has evolved and is applied in the protection and interpretation of human rights within the Nigerian, UK and South African legal systems.

6.1. Vulnerability in the United Kingdom Legal System

The UK legal system explicitly integrates vulnerability protections through the Human Rights Act⁷⁸, which domesticates the European Convention on Human Rights. UK courts apply ECtHR jurisprudence recognizing vulnerabilities in contexts such as asylum, detention, and welfare provision. For instance, in **R (DA and Others) v. Secretary of State for Work and Pensions**⁷⁹, the UK Supreme Court considered the disproportionate impact of welfare reforms on single mothers, engaging with concepts of vulnerability and substantive equality. Additionally, the Equality Act⁸⁰ imposes duties on public authorities to consider the needs of vulnerable groups. Though Fineman's universal vulnerability theory remains a subject of academic debate in the UK, it indirectly influences legal reasoning in areas of social welfare and public equality duties⁸¹.

The European Court of Human Rights has increasingly relied on the concept of vulnerability in its jurisprudence, particularly in cases related to domestic violence, police investigations, and public order⁸² scenarios. The court has recognized that the State has a positive obligation to protect individuals from harm, including harm perpetrated by non-state actors. This includes taking measures to prevent violence, providing adequate support and protection to victims, and holding perpetrators accountable, this obligation is grounded in the European Convention on Human Rights.

A critical analysis of relevant case law reveals that the concept of vulnerability has been instrumental in advancing human rights. For example, in **Opuz v Turkey**⁸³, the European Court of Human Rights recognized the state's obligation to protect individuals from domestic violence and the need for effective investigation and prosecution. Similarly, in **M.C. v Bulgaria**⁸⁴, the Court in delivering its judgment in 2003 emphasized the importance of effective investigation and prosecution in cases of rape and other forms of sexual violence.

The concept of vulnerability presents both opportunities and challenges in the UK's human rights landscape. It highlights the need for a nuanced approach to protecting vulnerable individuals and groups while promoting equality and human rights for all. In the UK, vulnerability is addressed

⁷⁷ Pope Francis n (68)

⁷⁸ United Kingdom: Human Rights Act 1998, C. 42

⁷⁹ [2019] UKSC 21

⁸⁰ United Kingdom: Equality Act 2010, C. 15

⁸¹ M. A. Fineman, *the Vulnerable Subject and the Responsive State*, Emory Law Journal, (2008) 60(2), 251–275.

⁸² Particularly in Articles 2,3,and 8

⁸³ App No 33401/02, ECHR 870; (2009) European Human Rights Law Reports (50 EHRR 28)

⁸⁴ App No. 39272/98, (2005) 40 EHRR 20; 15 BHRC 627

through various laws and regulations, including the Disability Discrimination Act,⁸⁵ Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) and Universal Periodic Review⁸⁶.

Key Developments in UK Law:

- a. Magna Carta⁸⁷: Established that subjects of the crown had legal rights and laws applied to everyone, including the monarch.
- b. Human Rights Act: Incorporated the European Convention on Human Rights into UK law, providing a framework for protecting vulnerable individuals.
- c. Equality Act: Streamlined laws protecting individuals from discrimination based on characteristics like age, disability, gender, and race.

6.2. Vulnerability in the South African Legal System

South Africa's Constitution⁸⁸ embeds vulnerability recognition through its progressive Bill of Rights, including socio-economic rights. The Constitutional Court frequently acknowledges the vulnerabilities of historically marginalized groups, integrating Fineman's universal vulnerability theory and Fredman's substantive equality model into its jurisprudence. In **Government of the Republic of South Africa v. Grootboom**⁸⁹, the Court emphasized the state's positive obligation to provide access to adequate housing for vulnerable communities. Furthermore, the court's interpretation of the right to dignity, equality, and socio-economic rights often explicitly engages with vulnerability reasoning. The influence of UN human rights bodies and the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights further strengthens South Africa's vulnerability-sensitive legal framework.

6.3. VULNERABILITY AS A PRINCIPLE OF INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION

The principle of vulnerability has been gradually integrated into the jurisprudence of human rights bodies. The European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR), and UN treaty bodies have all acknowledged that vulnerable groups such as children, persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples, and refugees require special protection beyond general human rights guarantees. This development reflects the recognition that abstract equality is insufficient without considering the lived realities of those most at risk. The European Court of Human Rights has increasingly relied on the concept of vulnerability in its jurisprudence, the court has recognized that the state has a positive obligation to protect individuals from harm, including harm perpetrated by non-state actors.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the concept of vulnerability is a fundamental aspect of contemporary human rights law, emphasizing the importance of recognizing and responding to the universal susceptibility to harm. Through a critical analysis of relevant case law and academic literature, this article has demonstrated the significance of vulnerability in advancing human rights. By recognizing the importance of collective responsibility in ensuring the protection of human rights, we can work towards a more just and equitable society where everyone's human rights are respected and protected.

The maxim "everything is connected and no one is saved alone" serves as a guiding principle for contemporary human rights law in an age of global interdependence. Recognizing vulnerability as a universal and relational condition compels legal systems to move beyond abstract formalism toward concrete solidarity. Human rights, in this sense, are not merely about protecting individuals in isolation but about sustaining the networks of interdependence that make human dignity possible, it affirms that

⁸⁵ United Kingdom: Disability Discrimination Act 1995, C. 50

⁸⁶ A History of Human Rights in Britain, Equality and Human Rights Commission Published 9 October 2018 www.equalityhumanrights.com accessed 16 June 2025

⁸⁷ Magna Carta (Great Charter) 1215, cl.39

⁸⁸ Constitution of the Republic of South Africa Act 108 of 1996

⁸⁹ 2001 (1) SA 46 (CC)

human rights cannot be fully realized in isolation but must be secured through cooperation, institutional responsiveness, and a commitment to global justice.

In a fragmented world, the promise of human rights will remain unfulfilled unless vulnerability is embraced as a foundational concept, reminding us that the security of one is bound to the security of all. Therefore, human rights law, when read through the lens of vulnerability, thus becomes not only a shield against violations but also a bridge toward a more just, interdependent, and humane order where dignity is shared, and survival is collective.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

- a. Strengthen State Responsibility:** States should take proactive measures to prevent human rights violations and protect individuals from harm
- b. Promote Intersectional Understanding:** States and human rights bodies should recognize and address the intersecting forms of discrimination and inequality that exacerbate vulnerability
- c. Foster A Culture of Human Rights:** States and civil society should work together to promote a culture of human rights, emphasizing the importance of dignity, equality, and respect for all individuals.

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